

THE EXAMINATION OF THE PERCEPTIONS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON SOCIAL INTEGRATIONⁱ

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Abstract:

The study was conducted to determine the secondary school students' perceptions on social integration and examine them in terms of certain variables. It was a descriptive study with survey methodology. The universe of the research consisted of the students studying at secondary schools in Mardin city center during 2016-2017 educational year. The sample included four distinctive schools and the participants were randomly selected among İmam Hatip High Schools, Anatolian High Schools, Science High Schools and Vocational and Technical High Schools. The data from 1035 students were collected from the randomly selected branches of the grade levels in the aforementioned schools. The data on the social integration levels of high school students were collected through the "Social Integration Scale". The research results indicated that the secondary school students had moderate level of perceptions with regard to social integration and the students' levels of social integration were in direct proportion with the educational quality and academic achievement of the students.

Keywords: social integration, secondary education, student, youth, high school

1. Introduction

Education is a chain of planned actions that helps to develop certain social processes or the behaviors of people that are effective in the development and socialization of

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individuals. The function of education is to provide social continuity through transferring the existing cultural values to new generations and to try to transform the behaviors of a child as a biological entity into a social entity (Dinçer, 2003). The educational systems are obliged to prepare the people they address to integrate with their society (Gişi et al., 2012).

The development of the individual and the continuity of the society depend on each other. The human nature can only flourish in the society. The individual and the community interact and depend on each other (Maclver and Page, 1969). The society has to impose and inoculate the common cultural values to every single individual to be able to sustain its very existence. It is not probable for the individual to maintain a life outside of the society. The interruption of socialization prevents the development of adult behaviors (Türkkahraman, 2009). The people are born and gain their social characteristics within social groups. The individuals also adopt knowledge and values within these groups that they need to live in the society. They become the members of a society as long as they embrace the accepted values and the existing information. In this context, being the member of a society is regarded as socialization. Besides, the socialization process makes it easier for the newborns to acknowledge the available culture and adapt to the existing environment. It is a process starting with the birth of man to the death (Güney, 2008). Above all, man is a social entity and social life is the outcome of his intellect and ability to think. The individual, on the one hand, follows the biological and bodily growth processes, on the other hand integrates with the norms of the society and becomes a member of the community in which he lives. As a result, human personality is shaped in the process of socialization (Arslantürk and Amman 2009). Social integration is the fundamental process in acquiring someone's personality. Human personality and society are inextricably linked to each other. The individual cannot be considered separate from the society and culture in which he lives; likewise, society and culture maintains the presence of reality and survive in the behaviors of individuals. Social values come into prominence in the formation of this reality (Beşirli, 2016).

While individuals are affected by society, they continue to influence it and try to become a member of the community they live in. Throughout their lives, they learn and embrace the elements of their society such as culture and values. From this point of view, it can be inferred that socialization involves the period of time the individual has spent to become a member of the society (Erkal, 2006; Şen, 2007). Socialization refers to the knowledge of the individual with regard to the requisites of the available culture, organization of society, division of labor, production and consumption patterns of the society in which he lives and to be in the effort of participating in these kinds of

processes through acquiring various knowledge, skills, values and behaviors (Özpolat, 2009). As the human being is a social entity, he must naturally live in a society. An individual's integration into society, identity development and respect for the societal values result from social integration.

Although the process of socialization sometimes involves conflict, it primarily refers to the absorption of the society's expectations by the members and putting them into practice. In this regard, the individual will be accepted and approved by the society when carrying out the attitudes, behaviors and beliefs in social life in parallel with the community expectations. The sound adaptation to society will also enable the young to integrate constructively with the other people and social values and to behave in accordance with the community expectations. The individuals' personal and social adaptation are linked to the community they live in. Therefore, family structure, circle of friends, school environment and television are the main factors that influence social adaptation of an adolescent (Avcı, 2006).

The individual's acceptance of social norms, values, beliefs, habits, tendencies and behavioral models of social life as a social entity takes place through politics, education, economy, culture and the other social institutions within the process of socialization (Dursun, 2012; İçli, 2005). The relationship network in the social environment is formed through various social institutions. The most important tasks of the institutions established in the society are to organize social relations and to maintain the existence and the continuity of the society (Aslan, 2001). Education is regarded as one of the most effective means of political, social and cultural integration and change management (MEB, 2005). The social integration of the students takes place through the family and the educational processes in which they learn the basic expectations of other people related to themselves.

Education contributes to social harmony only when it is applied for the purpose of integration to the values and the life style of the society in which the individual lives. While conveying the community's existing values, the primary function of educational institutions is to prepare and educate individuals who are capable of meeting the ideals and expectations for the future of the society. The balance created between the actual norms and values of the society and those desired to be acquired through education is essential for the society in terms of stability and organization. That's why the educational practices that have societal bases will eventually cultivate the people who will create and sustain the existence of the society. Therefore, in determining the aims of education in a society, individual and socio-cultural values should be considered and social competence should be taken into account (Tezcan, 1997). Consequently, educational institutions not only aim at transferring the cultural heritage from

generation to generation with the programs they implement, but they also help the individuals in the society to adapt to local and global happenings, new forms of behavior, changes and developments in science, art, technology, economy, sports, and the other areas as well as universal values and approaches. In other words, education takes the responsibilities of producing new information, disseminating information, conveying the cultural values of society to new generations, updating and improving the relevant information, inoculating democratic knowledge, attitudes and understanding to the individuals and providing them with knowledge and skills required by the society, supplying and facilitating the integration of the individual to the society and to the world. It can also be indicated that it is the responsibility of education to educate individuals who will be able to adapt to changes and then succeed in the renewed tasks and responsibilities (Şen, 2007).

Society and education are two complementary concepts. All the societies need educational institutions to survive. Education is the most important social institution created by society in order to maintain the regular societal life (Aslan, 2001). However, the education of the youth not only comprises the training of school and family institutions, but it also includes education with its surroundings and widespread socialization process (Duverger, 1998).

Though all the social institutions influence the socialization of the individual, it is mainly under the control of family, school, circle of friends, business circle, various religious, intellectual, cultural and professional groups due to their being the primary sources of social environment and information-culture (Özpolat, 2010). In particular, the school is of great importance as a continual socialization resource throughout the individual's life. From the beginning of childhood, the schools are regarded as one of the most important social resources (Pianta, 1992). The fulfillment of the schools' educational objectives effectively is vital in terms of sound individuals and sound societies. The school, after the family, is an important institution in the socialization of children and adolescents. In this sense, it has significant functions in the orientation of young people to future professions appropriate to their intelligence and abilities, in the transference of social values from generation to generation, in obtaining a status within the social order and in child and youth care and so on (Avcı, 2006). Similarly, Binbaşıoğlu (1990), who points out that the school is the place where the social characteristics that the child acquires in the family are developed more systematically, indicates that the child learns from the social activities established in the school to get along well with others, to express his emotions and thoughts, to respect the others' point of views, make others bow to his ideas, to respect the decisions of the community and to behave accordingly. In this regard, the school is a small example of social life, a

place where the skills of new generations are developed in a certain order, and an institution that helps the socialization of young people together with the family (Avcı, 2006).

While the school helps young people to develop and integrate to the society, it may also lead to divergent behaviors by adversely affecting the development of young people for several reasons. The inadequate physical conditions in schools together with the negative attitudes and behaviors arise from the deficiencies caused by the personality of teachers and their socio-economic level may cause students to lose their motivation towards the school, to escape from school, to exhibit actions with adjustment and behavior disorders towards school supplies, friends or teachers (Yörükoğlu, 1999). If the individual cannot maintain the social integration process properly, the youth can create, instead of high ideals, patterns such as frustration, aggressiveness and violence together with the desperate psychological-spiritual structures and introverted characteristics (Kasatura, 1998).

Many studies have been conducted on the students studying at secondary education institutions in Turkey. Some of them addressed the youth from social aspects such as educational status and working conditions, and some investigated the relationship between adolescents' personal, social and familial characteristics and self-acceptance levels. It can be argued that there are very few studies on the social integration perceptions of the students studying at secondary education institutions in Turkey. The determination of students' perceptions towards social integration is considered to contribute significantly to the development of social integration policies and educational projects to be implemented for secondary students. This study was conducted to determine whether the social integration perceptions of secondary school students differed in terms of certain variables. In line with this objective, the following questions were sought:

1. What are the social integration perceptions of secondary school students?
2. Are there meaningful differences between the secondary students' perceptions on normative, national, social-environmental, local, familial and educational integration?
3. Are there meaningful differences between secondary school students' perceptions of social integration according to the variables of the type of school, grade level, academic achievement and gender?

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

It was a descriptive study with survey methodology. These kind of studies aim to understand whether there is a dependent variance between two or more variables, and to find out the degree if that is the case (Karasar, 2010). These studies are conducted on a sample representing the universe and the existing circumstances are attempted to be described in detail (Karakaya, 2009).

2.2 Universe and Sample

The universe of the research consisted of the students studying at secondary schools in Artuklu District of Mardin (Turkey) in the academic year of 2016-2017. The universe included 22 secondary schools in total (five İmam Hatip High Schools, nine Anatolian High Schools, one Science High School and seven Vocational and Technical High Schools). Four schools (Imam Hatip High School, Anatolian High School, Science High School and Vocational and Technical High School) included in the sampling through random cluster sampling method. Random cluster sampling is a sampling method in which the clusters are randomly selected and also the units that form the sample are randomly selected among the clusters (Aypay, 2015). The total of 9260 students in the universe were stratified as the first, the second, the third and the fourth grades according to stratified sampling technique, the research data were collected from 1035 students on the basis of volunteerism from the randomly selected branches as there were more than one branch at each grade level in the specified schools. The universe representation rate of the sample was 11.2%.

As seen in Table 1, 24.6% (255) of the respondents were female and 75.4% (780) were male and among the grand total of 1035 participants, 319 (32.8%) of whom were studying at 9th grade, 247 (23.9%) were studying at 10th grade, 240 (23.2%) were studying at 11th grade and 209 (20.1%) were studying at 12th grade. The examination of the sample according to the type of school indicated that 299 students (28.9%) were studying at Anatolian High Schools, 198 students (19.2%) were studying at Science High Schools, 272 students (26.3%) were studying at Imam Hatip High Schools and 266 students (25.6%) were studying at Vocational and Technical High Schools. The examination of the respondents' grade point averages proved that 14.7% of them were between 0-59 points, 21.2% of them were between 60-69 points, 36.5% of them were between 70-84 points and 27.6% of them were between 85-100 points.

Table 1: Descriptive Properties of the Sample

Variable		N	%
Gender	Female	255	24.6
	Male	780	75.4
	Total	1035	
Grade level	9 th grade	339	32.8
	10 th grade	247	23.9
	11 th grade	240	23.2
	12 th grade	209	20.1
	Total	1035	
The type of school	Anatolian High Schools	299	28.9
	Science High Schools	198	19.2
	İmam Hatip High Schools	272	26.3
	Vocational and Technical High Schools	266	25.6
	Total	1035	
Grade Point Average	Between 0-59	147	14.7
	Between 60-69	211	21.2
	Between 70-84	364	36.5
	Between 85-100	275	27.6
	Total	997	

2.2 Data Collection and Data Analysis

The data on social integration levels of the secondary school students were collected through the Social Integration Scale (SIS) developed by Hüseyin Şimşek and Ahmet Salih Şimşek. The scale has six sub-dimensions including Normative and Moral integration, National integration, Familial integration, integration with Social Environment, Local integration and Educational integration and consists of five-point Likert-type 46 items. As a result of factor analysis applied to SIS, KMO value was estimated to be .95 and the Bartlett test was found to be meaningful ($2\chi = 22372,605$; $p < .05$). The total variance explained (validity) of the correlations for the sum of the scale was 47.792%. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient for the sub-dimensions of the scale was 0.90. The academic achievement scores of the students were defined in the Regulation on Secondary Education Institutions of the Ministry of National Education as follows: 0-49 points below passing mark, 50-59 points over passing mark. In data analysis, the Grade Point Averages of the students range from 0-59 were combined together. In data analysis, Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis H tests were applied due to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov value in the normality test indicated that the research data was not normally distributed ($p < .05$) and the variances were not homogeneous

(Pallant, 2007). Furthermore, arithmetic means, percentages and frequencies were also estimated beyond the statistics of the research.

3. Findings

Descriptive statistics on the secondary school students' levels of social integration and the sub-dimensions were presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Secondary School Students' Levels of Social Integration and the Sub-dimensions

Sub-dimensions	N	$\bar{x}$	SD
Integration with Social Environment	1035	3.49	.794
Local Integration	1034	3.14	1.107
Familial Integration	1034	4.01	.869
Educational Integration	1033	3.05	1.007
National Integration	1013	4.10	.890
Normative and Moral Integration	1013	4.10	.890
Total		3.60	.681

According to Table 2, the overall mean of the social integration perceptions of secondary school students was found to be at the level of agreement ($\bar{x} = 3.60$). When the means of sub-dimensions were examined, it was clear that National Integration and Normative and Moral Integration were the highest sub-dimensions ($\bar{x} = 4,10$) while Educational Integration and Local Integration sub-dimensions were the least.

Table 3: Kruskal Wallis-H Test Results about the Respondents' Social Integration Perceptions According to Grade Level

Variable	Grade Level	N	$\bar{x}$	$\bar{x}$ rank	Df	P	Meaningful differences
	9 th Grade	339	3.38	458.17			(1-4)
	10 th Grade	247	3.53	521.59	3	.000*	(2-4)

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Integration with Social Environment	11 th Grade	240	3.48	527.47			
	12 th Grade	209	3.70	599.93			
Local Integration	9 th Grade	339	3.44	599.79			(1-2)
	10 th Grade	246	3.01	481.99	3	.000*	(1-3)
	11 th Grade	240	3.07	505.28			(1-4)
	12 th Grade	209	2.86	439.84			
Familial Integration	9 th Grade	339	4.19	565.50			(1-3)
	10 th Grade	246	4.03	521.93	3	.000*	(1-4)
	11 th Grade	240	3.88	479.73			
	12 th Grade	209	3.89	477.79			
Educational Integration	9 th Grade	338	3.48	634.61			(1-2)
	10 th Grade	246	2.94	486.35	3	.000*	(1-3)
	11 th Grade	240	3.97	490.89			(1-4)
	12 th Grade	209	2.63	392.84			(2-4),(3-4)
National Integration	9 th Grade	322	4.09	487.34			
	10 th Grade	245	4.10	501.81	3	.157	
	11 th Grade	237	4.01	505.16			
	12 th Grade	209	4.18	545.46			
Normative and Moral Integration	9 th Grade	322	4.09	487.34			
	10 th Grade	245	4.10	501.81	3	.157	
	11 th Grade	237	4.01	505.16			
	12 th Grade	209	4.18	545.16			

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Total	9 th Grade	339	3.76	572.88			(1-2)
	10 th Grade	247	3.57	499.03	3	.000*	(1-3)
	11 th Grade	240	3.53	505.17			(1-4)
	12 th Grade	209	3.50	466.12			
*p<.05		1035					

According to Table 3, there were meaningful differences between the social integration perceptions of the students according to the variable of grade levels. The examination of the results on the basis of sub-dimensions indicated that there were meaningful differences between integration with social environment, local integration, familial integration and educational integration scores according to grade levels the students study, but there were no meaningful differences in the sub-dimensions of normative and moral integration and national integration. As a result of the Tukey HSD test to determine the source of differences, there were significant differences between the 9th and 10th grades, 11th and 12th grades in the overall social integration scores and it was clear that the difference was in favor of the 9th grade students. It can be argued that the 9th grade students' level of social integration was significantly higher than that of the remaining grade levels. In addition, the 12th grade students were found to have the lowest means in terms of overall social integration scores.

Table 4: Kruskal Wallis-H Test Results about the Respondents' Social Integration Perceptions According to the Type of School

Variable	Type of School	N	$\bar{x}$	$\bar{x}$ rank	Df	P	Meaningful differences
Integration with Social Environment	Anatolian High Schools	299	3.55	544.54			(1-2)
	Science High Schools	198	3.75	624.03	3	.000*	(2-3)
	Imam Hatip High Schools	272	3.28	426.64			(3-4)
	Vocational and Technical High Schools	266	3.48	502.66			(1-3)
Local Integration	Anatolian High Schools	299	2.94	467.36			
	Science High Schools	198	2.95	466.56	3	.000*	(1-3)

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		Schools						
Familial Integration	Imam Hatip High Schools	272	3.42	594.72			(2-3)	
	Vocational and Technical High Schools	265	3.19	532.88				
	Anatolian High Schools	299	3.80	449.02			(1-2)	
	Science High Schools	198	4.20	584.38	3	.000*	(1-3)	
	Imam Hatip High Schools	272	4.08	526.43			(1-4)	
	Vocational and Technical High Schools	265	4.06	535.63				
	Anatolian High Schools	299	2.77	438.24			(2-3)	
	Science High Schools	198	2.81	441.60	3	.000*	(1-3)	
	Imam Hatip High Schools	271	3.32	584.00			(1-4)	
	Vocational and Technical High Schools	265	3.30	593.69			(2-4)	
	National Integration	Anatolian High Schools	298	4.05	494.62			(1-2)
		High Schools	198	4.37	614.53	3	.000*	(2-3)
Science High Schools		255	3.91	431.28			(3-4)	
Schools		262	4.12	513.51				
Imam Hatip High Schools								
Vocational and Technical High Schools								
Normative and Moral Integration	Anatolian High Schools	298	4.05	494.62			(1-2)	
	High Schools	198	4.37	614.53	3	.000*	(2-3)	
	Science High Schools	255	3.91	431.28			(3-4)	
	Schools	262	4.12	513.51				
	Imam Hatip High Schools							
	Vocational and							

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Technical High Schools.						
Toplam	Anatolian High Schools	299	3.48	471.42		(1-4)
	Science High Schools	198	3.59	504.44	3	.000*
	Imam Hatip High Schools	272	3.65	519.36		
	Vocational and Technical High Schools	266	3.73	579.06		
	Total	1035				

*p<.05

According to Table 4, there were meaningful differences between the social integration perceptions of the students according to the variable of the type of school. The examination of the results on the basis of sub-dimensions indicated that there were meaningful differences between the scores of all the dimensions, namely integration with social environment, local integration, familial integration, educational integration, normative and moral integration and national integration, according to the type of school. As a result of the Tukey HSD test to determine the source of meaningful differences, meaningful differences were determined between the students studying at Anatolian High Schools and those at İmam Hatip High Schools and Vocational and Technical High Schools in favor of İmam Hatip High Schools and Vocational and Technical High Schools. When the students studying at Science High Schools were examined on the basis of sub-dimensions, it was found that they had a higher level of perception in comparison with the remaining groups in all but local integration and educational integration, namely in the sub-dimensions of social integration, familial integration, national integration and normative and moral integration. According to these findings, it can be inferred that the social integration levels of the students studying at Science High Schools were relatively higher. Besides, it was a remarkable finding that the students studying at Science High Schools had a low mean in the sub-dimension of educational integration.

Table 5: Kruskal Wallis-H Test Results about the Respondents' Social Integration Perceptions
 According to Academic Achievement

Variable	Academic Achievement	N	$\bar{x}$	$\bar{x}$ rank	Df	P	Meaningful differences
Integration with Social Environment	Between 0-59	147	3.31	415.93	3	.000*	(1-3)
	Between 60-69	211	3.39	459.05			(1-4)
	Between 70-84	364	3.51	501.94			(2-4)
	Between 85-100	275	3.68	570.17			
Local Integration	Between 0-59	147	3.19	511.92	3	.353	
	Between 60-69	210	3.02	467.99			
	Between 70-84	364	3.17	509.89			
	Between 85-100	275	3.14	499.55			
Familial Integration	Between 0-59	147	3.87	453.93	3	.025	
	Between 60-69	210	3.97	473.71			
	Between 70-84	364	4.04	504.33			
	Between 85-100	275	4.11	533.54			
Educational Integration	Between 0-59	147	3.06	500.51	3	.296	
	Between 60-69	209	3.03	490.16			
	Between 70-84	364	3.13	518.46			
	Between 85-100	275	2.97	475.53			
National Integration	Between 0-59	141	4.02	443.53	3	.004*	(1-4)
	Between 60-69	207	4.04	464.30			
	Between 70-84	354	4.09	482.64			
	Between 85-100	273	4.19	535.89			
Normative and Moral Integration	Between 0-59	141	4.02	443.53	3	.004*	(1-4)
	Between 60-69	207	4.04	464.30			
	Between 70-84	354	4.09	482.64			
	Between 85-100	273	4.19	535.89			
Total	Between 0-59	147	3.53	460.43	3	.191	
	Between 60-69	211	3.57	486.74			
	Between 70-84	364	3.65	518.51			
	Between 85-100	275	3.61	503.20			
	Total	997					

*p<.05

According to Table 5, there were no meaningful differences between the overall sum of the social integration perceptions of the students according to the variable of academic

achievement. The examination of the results on the basis of sub-dimensions indicated that there were meaningful differences in the sub-dimensions of integration with social environment, national integration and normative and moral integration. No meaningful differences were determined in the sub-dimensions of local integration, familial integration and educational integration. As a result of the Tukey HSD test to determine the source of differences, the difference in the sub-dimensions of national integration and normative and moral integration were between the clusters of 0-59 points and 85-100 points. It was in favor of the students whose grade point averages were between 85-100 points. In the dimension of integration with social environment, the students whose grade point averages were between 0-59 points had the lowest average, while the highest average belonged to the students whose grade point averages were between 70-100 points. It can be claimed that the students with high grade point averages had higher levels of social integration perceptions.

Table 6: Mann-Whitney U Test Results about the Respondents' Social Integration Perceptions According to Gender

Variable	Gender	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	T	P
Integration with Social Environment	Female	255	3.59	.817	2.241	.008
	Male	780	3.46	.784		
Local Integration	Female	255	2.85	1.159	-4.785	.000*
	Male	779	3.23	1.074		
Familial Integration	Female	255	3.84	.969	-3643	.000*
	Male	779	4.07	.826		
Educational Integration	Female	255	2.77	1.071	-5163	.000*
	Male	778	3.14	.969		
National Integration	Female	254	4.14	.958	817	.069
	Male	759	4.08	.866		
Normative and Moral Integration	Female	254	4.14	.958	817	.069
	Male	759	4.08	.866		
Total	Female	255	3.48	.753	-3.190	.004*
	Male	780	3.64	.652		
	Total	1035				

*p<.05

According to Table 6, there were meaningful differences between the social integration perceptions of the students according to the variable of gender. The examination of the results on the basis of sub-dimensions indicated that there were no meaningful differences in the sub-dimensions of integration with social environment, national integration and moral integration and national integration. Meaningful differences were determined in the sub-dimensions of local integration, familial integration and educational integration. As a result of the Tukey HSD test to determine the source of differences, the differences in local integration, familial integration and educational integration were found to be in favor of male students. In all of the sub-dimensions, the means of male students were higher than those of females. It can be asserted that male students studying at high schools had higher levels of social integration perceptions in comparison with their female counterparts.

4. Discussion

It was concluded that the social integration perceptions of the secondary school students were at a moderate level. On the basis of sub-dimensions, it was determined that the levels of Normative and Moral Integration, Familial Integration and National Integration were high but the levels of Educational integration and Local integration were low. In their study, Şimşek and Şimşek (2013) extrapolated that National Integration and Normative and Moral Integration were the sub-dimensions that the students integrated most. They also found that the lowest level of integration of the students was in the sub-dimension of Educational Integration. In this respect, the results of this study overlap with Şimşek and Şimşek's (2013) research.

Recent studies by KONDA research company, A & G Company, Seta Foundation and Bahçeşehir University found that Normative and Moral Values had high acceptance rates in the society. According to the research conducted in 2010 for the Southeastern Anatolia region by Bahçeşehir University, the respondents declared that religious belief by 89.9% and family by 88.8% were indispensable for themselves (<http://busam.bahcesehir.edu.tr>). It can be claimed that the high level of Normative and Moral Integration and Familial Integration of the secondary school students in this study had a positive effect on the level of National Integration as the family has a very important role in the socialization of a child. The family clarifies the individual with many activities and habits by shaping the child according to the socio-cultural expectations of the society (Orwin, 1997). In other words, the family that is the core of society is a school of socialization. The socialization of an individual begins in the family. The fact that what is learned in life is built on the existing knowledge, values

and skills, that it takes place in the family setting and that the family is a lifelong living space for many people demonstrate the importance of the socialization process operated in the family (Özpolat, 2010). The family is the founding unit of the individual-society relation in Turkey. In sum, Turkish society is based on family organization (Doğan, 2009). In addition, social support of the family has positive effects on the level of self-acceptance of a student. Akın and Ceyhan (2005) found that students with high levels of perceived social support from their families had higher levels of self-acceptance. It emerged that communication within the family based on sharing, love, and attention, the parents' respect and guidance for the adolescent's efforts of independence, their tolerance, acceptance and supportive attitudes to the problems experienced in the quite complicated adolescence period made significant contributions to the self-development and the self-acceptance process of the adolescent.

Moral norms contribute to social integration by ensuring the sound process of social institutions and the socialization of the individual. While moral norms provide the religious socialization and cultivation of the individual, they also perform a lot of social functions from the provision of social unity and integrity to the protection of social ethics and values (Göçeri, 2002). The high level of normative and moral integration can be interpreted as the secondary school students' acceptance of the normative and moral values to a great extent.

In the study, the students' perceptions of Educational Integration were found to be low. Şimşek and Şimşek (2013) also reported a low level of educational integration in their research. According to the results of Kalaycı and Özdemir (2013) and Arastaman (2009), the students' level of commitment to the school found to be at a moderate level. These findings implied that there is a problem between students and school expectations and the students are not satisfied with the school and the educational system on a wider basis. This may be due to various factors such as physical structure of the school, inadequate equipment of the school, teachers, school administrators and curriculum. Together with the family, the school is a fundamental element of an educational system and the most important institution in the socialization of children and youth. In this regard, it has significant functions in the orientation of young people to future professions appropriate to their intelligence and abilities, in the transference of social values from generation to generation, in obtaining a status within the social order and in child and youth care. On the other hand, the educational system is a holistic structure in which education-related practices are designed and practiced via the schools. Therefore, the existence of a favorable educational system will constitute convenient grounds for the cultivation of socio-psychologically compatible and mentally healthy individuals (Avcı, 2006). While the school helps young people to

develop and integrate to society, it may also lead to divergent behaviors by adversely affecting the development of young people for several reasons. The factors that adversely influencing the school and the education are the teacher's being tolerant or authoritarian, low socio-economic status and high course load, overcrowded classes, heterogeneous classes full of the students with different levels of intelligence and maturity, the family backgrounds and the socio-economic status of the students, the location of the school and the attitude of school administration towards students (Yörükoğlu, 1994). Unfavourable physical conditions at schools together with the negative attitudes and behaviors arise from the personality disorders of teachers and their socio-economic status may cause students to lose their motivation towards school, to escape from school, to exhibit actions with adjustment and behavior disorders towards school supplies, friends or teachers (Avcı, 2006). These kinds of problems caused by education and school may lead to the breakdown of the students' beliefs in the society and in the future. An individual's losing faith, as a source of weakness, will lead to the transformation into destructive power with the idea of trying to treat the impairment of human balance with the ability to stimulate due to certain reasons such as weakness, anxiety and inefficacy. In other words, the individual may be oriented towards a sort of compensatory violence that rise from weakness as the individual who do not create is claimed to destroy (Fromm, 1994). All of these factors may cause students to develop social, cultural and psychological problems and the socialization process to be adversely affected.

It was concluded that there was a significant difference in the social integration perceptions of the secondary school students according to grade levels. The examination of the results on the basis of sub-dimensions indicated that there were meaningful differences between integration with social environment, local integration, familial integration and educational integration scores according to grade levels the students study but there were no meaningful differences in the sub-dimensions of normative and moral integration and national integration. The 9th grade students were found to have the highest means in terms of overall social integration scores while the 12th grade students were with the lowest means. Şimşek and Şimşek (2013) also found a similar difference in the overall scores according to grade levels. Durmaz (2008) extrapolated that 9th grade students' perceptions with regard to life quality in high schools were statistically significantly higher than the other clusters. As the grade level increased, the level of social integration decreased among the students. In addition, Kutsal and Bilge (2012) concluded that the level of burnout increased relatively together with an increase in the grade levels, and the level of emotional exhaustion and losing faith in the 12th grade students were relatively higher than those of the 9th, 10th and 11th

grade students. These research results indicate that the 9th grade students have a high level of social integration and the 12th grade students have a relatively low level of social integration. The 12th grade students' more intensive academic schedule due to the upcoming university entrance exams together with their concerns about their future due to the end of compulsory school life may have had a great impact upon these findings.

As a result of the research, it was concluded that the secondary school students' perceptions related to the items of *"I am satisfied with today's education system"*, *"I am satisfied with my teachers at this very school"*, *"I'm going to school willingly"* and *"I am satisfied with the lessons and their contents at this school"* were found to be low. The favourable perception of the students towards teachers is very important for students' commitment to the school and for the socialization processes. Brewster and Bowen (2004) found that teacher support for middle and high school students increased the academic achievement levels of the students. Therefore, it was determined that particularly the sub-dimensions of the students' internal commitment towards the school and the relationship with the teacher were relatively important about the students' commitment to the school. When all these research results are taken into consideration, it is clear that the today's schools cannot meet the expectations of the secondary education students, do not provide them with favorable opportunities to unearth their talents and do not assist them to solve their problems as it is expected despite the fact that the secondary education students come to school willingly; thus it can be claimed that the low level of educational integration arise from ineffective management and malfunctioning of educational institutions to a great extent.

It was concluded that there was a significant difference in the social integration perceptions of the secondary school students according to the type of school they study. The examination of the results on the basis of sub-dimensions indicated that there were meaningful differences between integration with social environment, local integration, familial integration, educational integration, normative and moral integration and national integration scores according to the type of school. The students of Vocational and Technical High Schools were found to have the highest means in terms of overall social integration scores while the students of Anatolian High Schools were with the lowest means. The students of Science High Schools had a low mean in the sub-dimension of educational integration. As the students of Science High Schools do not go to school willingly and do not have favorable opportunities to unearth their talents, their perception related to the feeling of being a part of the school remained low. The research conducted in Edirne Science High School also proved that while the respondents attributed the feature of *"a home of science"* to Science High Schools in

general, they opined that these schools deviated from their ultimate aim as the success criterion of Science High Schools was started to be regarded as a vehicle to meet the individual's higher education expectations. The participants also stated that the pressure experienced in families and at school to succeed increased the students' levels of stress and anxiety and prevented their socialization. As a result of the study conducted by Edirne Science High School guidance unit, it was determined that the participants regarded the students' needs for social activities as the most important problem of the school (Edirne Science High School, 1999). In a survey conducted by the Ministry of National Education, most of the students studying at Science High Schools expressed that the number of social, cultural and sports activities was inadequate and thus their participation was weak. In the research conducted by the department in charge of Science High Schools of the Ministry of National Education, it was revealed that the Science High Schools were the least successful schools in sports activities organized throughout Turkey (MEB, 2001).

It was concluded that there was a significant difference in the social integration perceptions of the secondary school students according to academic achievement. However, Şimşek and Şimşek (2013) extrapolated that the grade point averages did not have a meaningful difference regarding the social integration perceptions. The examination of the results on the basis of sub-dimensions of academic achievement indicated that the students with grade point averages between 85 and 100 were found to have high means in terms of overall social integration scores. Academic achievement has a positive impact upon social integration. According to Arı (2003), academic achievement can be considered as a prominent factor in the identity development process of the adolescents. Thanks to achievement, adolescents may develop the sense of competence and self-worth, which are important identity elements, and increase their self-esteem. Besides, academic achievement is a factor in increasing social acceptance. According to Balkaya ve Ceyhan (2007), the evaluation of the pupils according to academic achievement by the family, teachers and society may also affect the own self-evaluation of the young. The academically successful students' exposure to more attention and acceptance in the family and school environment may support their identity development. On the other hand, low academic achievement can lead to behavioral problems, child maltreatment, aggressive behaviors, introversion, alienation towards teachers, parents, and peers. In this research, academic achievement may have created positive effects on the identity development of the adolescents through increased self-respect contributing to school achievement. To sum up, it can be inferred that academic achievement is directly proportionate to the individual's socialization

process and the students with high academic achievement have higher levels of self-acceptance and socialization.

It was concluded that there was a significant difference in the social integration perceptions of the secondary school students according to gender. The male students had higher levels of social integration perceptions in comparison with female students. Balkaya and Ceyhan (2007) found that the high school students' level of identity development did not differ according to gender. According to the results of Independent Samples T-Test in Sari's (2013) study conducted to examine the students' sense of belonging to the school according to gender, the differences between the means of the groups were not statistically significant but the means of female students for the overall scores of belonging to school were higher than those of their male counterparts.

It was concluded that the secondary school students' perceptions on local integration were lower than those of other sub-dimensions. While the respondents' perceptions related to the item of *"I am satisfied with living in this region"* were moderate, their perceptions were found to be low for the item of *"Even if I have the possibility to live elsewhere, I prefer living here"*. The respondents' low perception of local integration may have stemmed from the various economic problems in the city where the research was conducted or the security problems experienced in the region. The size of the settlement (city center, town or village) and the socio-economic level (poor or rich neighborhood) determine the nature of social relations between people. In other words, the location leads to a form of socialization built with its own socio-cultural characteristics. In this regard, the relationships established with the other people during childhood or youth have had an impact upon the attitudes, thoughts and behaviors of the individual over the course of time (Avcı, 2006). In this very context, it is pointed out that the resided location may be defined with attractive features of a city, liberal atmosphere of a city, being a member of a large group, the pride of being a member of a big city and so on (Suavi, 2000). The children's well-being is related to the physical conditions of the city in terms of providing social, cultural and sports activities to create opportunities for them to realize themselves. The environment is leading among the factors that determine the well-being of the child. It is very important for these kinds of facilities to provide support for the child and to enhance the social life. The quality of the cities' physical conditions in which the schools are located are also important for the students to have a positive life experience and to yield well-being.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The secondary school students' perceptions pertaining to National Integration, Normative and Moral Integration and Familial Integration are found to be high. The secondary school students are committed to social values and institutions. They adopt the society in which they live to a great extent. It is concluded that the secondary school students are satisfied with living in Turkey, will be happy to work for their country, perceive the moral values as meaningful in their personal lives and happy to live with their families. It can be pointed out that the students have high levels of national integration and citizenship consciousness and they are sensitive to national values.

The secondary school students' perceptions pertaining to Educational Integration and Local Integration are found to be low. It is concluded that despite going to school willingly, the students are not satisfied with the educational system, the school, the lessons and their contents, they do not always receive the help they need to solve the problems at school and there are no opportunities to unearth their talents at school. It can be inferred that secondary schools cannot meet the interests and expectations of the students satisfactorily. Furthermore, they indicate that the schools do not fulfill their objectives pertaining to social integration and are ineffective in terms of socialization to some extent.

In light of research results, the following recommendations are provided for educational policy practitioners, educators and researchers:

- To develop policies that will increase the level of consciousness pertaining to National Integration by turning the secondary education students' unforeseen high level of National Integration into an opportunity.
- To make all components of the school (School administrator, teachers, family, socio-cultural activities, curriculum, materials, decision making process, school culture, etc.) compatible with the student-centered educational approach to increase the level of Educational Integration.
- The school administration's and teachers' focus on the students with low academic achievement by operationalizing psychological counseling and guidance services and establishing a dialogue platform among teachers, students and their families in relation to the always-needed help in solving school problems through the elimination of test anxiety and the fear of failure. For this purpose, organizing activities such as educational seminars and conferences to develop the communication among parents, teachers and teenagers.

- Given that, the relatively low level of local integration can be attributed to the socio-economical underdevelopment of the region, to develop public policies that will increase the attractiveness of the region for the young.
- For researchers, it is advisable to conduct similar researches for different levels of educational institutions (preschool, primary school, university etc.) and also the studies for the level of social integration between the groups constituting the school community (teachers, parents, civil society and public institutions).

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